

EARTH SCIENCES

CHARACTERISTICS OF REAL ESTATE CADASTRES

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Abstract

The article outlines the importance and effectiveness of the real estate cadastre, as well as information about new cadastral technologies. In addition, cadastral registration of real estate and their systematization were reflected here.

Keywords: real estate, cadastre, geographic information systems, electronic cadastral maps.

Real estate cadastre - includes all information, including rights and restrictions on real estate objects. Compilation and maintenance of a single cadastre of immovable property serves a number of purposes [2]:

- Accelerating the organization of electronic government by switching to the automated system of managing real estate objects;
- Recognition and protection of these rights by state registration of existing rights on all types of immovable property that are the object of cadastral accounting in the territory of the Republic of Azerbaijan, regardless of the form of ownership and purpose;
- Conducting cadastral accounting of real estate objects, creating a cadastre of registered real estate in order to regularize the existing illegal buildings in the territory of the Republic of Azerbaijan;
- Ensuring taxation of immovable property in the territory of the Republic of Azerbaijan;
- provision of flexibility in adaptation of real estate objects to the current market and study of internal market needs;
- provision of state registration of rights on real estate and contracts concluded in connection with them;
- drawing up cadastrals of newly formed real estate objects and involving the private sector in this field;
- using data from the real estate cadastral database as a separate service area;
- preservation of state-owned real estate objects and organization of their efficient use;
- drawing up digital cadastral maps of real estate within the administrative territory and cadastral division of the Republic of Azerbaijan on the basis of a single cadastral database of real estate;
- Compilation of the address register, mass inventory and assessment works in the territory of the Republic;
- provision of promptness in the operation of various service areas, as well as during the operation of emergency medical aid, emergencies and other services, prevention of unnecessary time loss;
- ensuring efficient use of real estate objects in the free market economy and ensuring their multi-purpose use;

- reduction of disputes related to real estate objects and facilitation of settlement of those disputes;
- efficient management of natural resources;
- management of relevant communications;
- monitoring of various types of real estate objects;
- preparation of complete statistical data on real estate objects.

Real estate cadastre is compiled and managed on the basis of modern geoinformation (GIS) technologies [3,4]. With the help of geographic information systems, there are opportunities to integrate graphic and text data. In this system, the basic data of the real estate cadastre are linked to the corresponding addresses on digital maps or plans. The reliable and perfect construction of this system depends on the description of the cadastral data model, which reflects the composition and structure of the cadastral data.

A considerable amount of cadastral data has been collected in paper format in the bodies that carry out individual sectoral cadastre in Azerbaijan, and due to the smallness and variety of these data, it is difficult to manage and monitor them, as well as to exchange information between sectoral bodies.

In the modern era, digital cadastral data of real estate is considered an important, unique and sometimes the only factor in the implementation of strategic and operational issues resolved by state authorities and local self-government bodies in order to protect the sovereignty and territorial integrity of Azerbaijan and ensure sustainable political, economic and social development. [1].

Currently, the real estate digital information system is used. As we know, the digital cadastral information system of real estate involves compiling cadastrals of real estate objects in the country, preparing electronic cadastral maps, and achieving the organization of automated cadastral services. The goal of all these works is, of course, to create a centralized single cadastral data bank, to achieve scientific management of real estate objects in the country by using the materials and data of this bank and the application of information and communication technologies. Unified state cadastral works of immovable property, which are intended to be carried out continuously, will allow cadastral data to be

complete, accurate, comprehensive, and cadastral objects to be comprehensively characterized as management objects. At the same time, the cadastral data bank will enable the exchange of information between individual executive bodies in accordance with their duties and functions. The organization of cadastral works in this way will turn cadastral activity into one of the service infrastructures necessary for the effective functioning of the emerging electronic government [6].

As a result, the cadastral registration of real estate objects is carried out according to the following procedures:

- 1) Conducting preliminary research on the cadastral registration of real estate objects;
- 2) Implementation of cadastral accounting works:
 - determination of boundaries of land plots and real estate objects on them;
 - personalization of real estate objects;
 - drawing up the technical passport of the real estate object.

3) Registration of real estate objects in the cadastral register (individual, quantitative and qualitative indicators).

Information about immovable properties registered in the cadastral register is systematized in a single cadastral database of immovable property.

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